

The Influence of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Sales Promotion, and Hedonic Motivation on Continuance Intention Through Attitude: A Study on Shopee Marketplace Users in East Java- Indonesia

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Abstract

The marketplace is growing rapidly in Indonesia. It is important to further understand consumers' intentions to continue using the marketplace platform because the sustainability of the marketplace depends on the continuity of consumers' intentions to keep using it. The goal of this study is to examine the influences of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, sales promotion, hedonic motivation on continuance intention through attitude. The sample for this study consists of Shopee application users in East Java and 240 respondents were obtained. Researchers used an online questionnaire as a data collection method, which was then analyzed using the PLS-based SEM method. The findings of this research indicate that perceived ease of use, sales promotion, and hedonic motivation have a significant effect on attitude and continuance intention. Attitude also plays a mediating role in the relationship between perceived ease of use, sales promotion, and hedonic motivation toward continuance intention, excluding perceived usefulness. On the other hand, perceived usefulness does not significantly affect attitude and continuance intention.

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1. Introduction

The impact of the fourth industrial revolution on the economy has been evident in the rapid technological transformation. This swift development, such as internet progress, is significantly felt by the Indonesian society. As revealed in the APJII 2023 survey, the number of Indonesians connected to the internet in 2023 increased from the previous year by 215 million people, out of a total population of 278,690,000, with an internet penetration rate in Indonesia of 78.19%. Java Island contributed the most, reaching 58.62% of the total contribution, led by West Java with the highest contribution at 18.93% and a penetration rate of 82.73%. Meanwhile, East Java followed with a contribution of 15.58% and a penetration rate of 81.26% (Survei APJII, 2023). Indonesia ranks third in Asia in the number of internet users, reaching 212.4 million people in July 2022 (Databoks, 2022b), as shown in Figure 1.1.

Source: Databoks, 2022

Figure 1. The Number of Internet Users in Indonesia in Asia (in million) (Google Maps, 2023)

In today's modern life, with the massive penetration of internet users in Indonesia, easy, fast, and affordable internet access has become a fundamental need. This has led to a change in the lifestyle of the community as the internet is used to support various activities, especially economic and business transactions that are increasingly digital-based. The surge in internet users in Indonesia has been a primary catalyst for the growth of digital businesses across various sectors, particularly in the development of online shopping businesses (Palinggi & Limbongan, 2020). Many people choose to shop online to meet their needs because it is more cost-effective, time-saving, and energy-efficient (Azzahra, 2023). Online shopping platform are the most flexible purchasing method, providing access that can be done anytime and anywhere, they also offer consumers the ability to easily gather information before making a purchase decision, such as comparing features, characteristics, and product prices (Chetioui et al., 2021).

The development of online shopping has spread rapidly in several countries, especially in Indonesia. Based on the survey results from We Are Social, Indonesia ranks first with the highest percentage of usage of online shopping providers in the world, and in the past few months, 88.1% of Internet users in Indonesia have used the services of online shopping providers to purchase specific products (Databoks, 2021). Based on the results of the Digital 2022 Global Overview Report survey, Indonesia ranks fifth in the world in terms of the frequency of online shopping every week. A total of 36% of consumer internet users in Indonesia actively use online shopping services (Databoks, 2022a). Bank Indonesia recorded the value of online shopping transactions through e-commerce and marketplaces in 2022, reaching 476.5 trillion, which increased by 18.8% compared to the previous year (Amanda, 2023).

Until now, the rapidly growing digital business transactions in Indonesia are online shopping through digital platforms. Sales through digital platforms combine online stores with digitally traded goods, allowing consumers to shop without having to travel long distances. These digital buying and selling platforms can be accessed through smartphones, which have become the primary device for the majority of the population (Bostoen, 2019). One of the various online trading platforms enriching the online shopping business in Indonesia is the Shopee marketplace. Shopee adopts a business model that focuses on connecting buyers with various sellers who offer their products and services in one place. Shopee is known as an online shopping platform that primarily focuses on being the first mobile marketplace platform in the consumer-to-consumer (C2C) category. The site offers a safe, enjoyable, and practical shopping experience, enabling users to buy and sell directly through their mobile phones. Shopee is a mobile marketplace application with a consumer-to-consumer (C2C) concept that provides a safe and convenient platform for buying and selling. Shopee offers a variety of products to meet daily needs, including fashion, gadgets, cosmetics, electronics, household appliances, and shopping vouchers. Additionally, Shopee consistently offers various large-scale promotions to attract customers, with free shipping being one of the most popular (Hermawan, 2023). The competition among online shopping sites in Indonesia has become increasingly fierce lately. According to The Map of E-commerce in Indonesia report published by iPrice, in the fourth quarter of 2019, the Shopee marketplace held the top rank, but from the fourth quarter of 2021 to the second quarter of 2022, it experienced a decline and held the second position. However, in terms of app rankings on both Google Play Store and App Store, Shopee outperformed by securing the top spot. Shopee is noted as the number 1 online shopping platform in Indonesia for total downloads in both Google Play Store and Apple App Store, as well as being the number 1 online shopping platform in terms of monthly active users (iPrice, 2023). Meanwhile, data from Databoks, indicates that the Shopee marketplace has achieved a growth of 166.9 million visits per month. It can be observed that Shopee outperforms its competitors and has reclaimed the number 1 position (Ahdiat, 2023).

The fluctuating development of online shopping platforms in Indonesia reflects an increasingly intense competition. Currently, marketplace companies are competing fiercely to capture consumer attention, considering how crucial consumers are as the primary foundation for boosting the revenue and profitability of the companies. One way to retain existing customers and acquire new ones is by enhancing the continuance intention of consumers in using the application for online shopping in the marketplace (Gorji & Siami, 2020). This indicates that continuance intention is a crucial factor that needs to be prioritized by marketplace companies so that their applications can compete with an increasing number of competitors and the growing innovation in the industry. Regarding continuance intention towards the marketplace, consumers will engage in continuance intention after initial transactions or usage, and when they perceive benefits, they decide to continue using the same marketplace (Nurjanah et al., 2023). In developing services or products based on technology, understanding how consumers interact with new technologies such as marketplaces is crucial. The long-term viability of information systems and technologies like marketplaces depends on the sustained intention of consumers to continue utilizing them (Devrinno et al., 2023).

Certainly, there are factors that can influence and enhance continuance intention in consumers, including the acceptance of technology by consumers, which leads to consumer behavioral intent to engage in online shopping on marketplaces. Referring to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) theory developed by Davis, the consumer's continued intention to use a system or information technology is determined by two main factors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The TAM theory with variables like perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use is a robust framework for examining the adoption of technology in online shopping applications on smartphones (Jiang et al., 2022). Perceived usefulness is defined as the extent to which an individual believes that using a

particular system or technology can help improve their performance because the system or technology is beneficial (Davis, 1989). This is supported by empirical evidence in previous research shows that perceived usefulness influences continuance intention, where perceived usefulness is a crucial factor in determining consumers' continued intention towards online purchasing and usage (Daneji et al., 2019; Dayal & Palsapure, 2020; Nugraheni et al., 2020; Omotayo & Omotope, 2018), however on the other hand there is still research which finds show that perceived usefulness has no effect on continuance intention (Ferdianto, 2022; Sarkar & Khare, 2019; Utami et al., 2022).

Another factor is the variable of perceived ease of use, which is defined as the extent to which an individual believes that a particular system or technology is easy to use (Davis, 1989). If consumers perceive ease of use in using the online shopping platform, it will make them feel satisfied because it is easily understandable and user-friendly, therefore, the formation of a positive perceived ease of use in consumers will encourage positive consumer continuance intention (Nabila et al., 2023). This is supported by empirical evidence in previous research shows that perceived ease of use influences continuance intention (Nugraheni et al., 2020; Omotayo & Omotope, 2018). However, the findings of that study contradict with some researchers who state that perceived ease of use does not have a significant impact on continuance intention (Ashfaq et al., 2019; Dayal & Palsapure, 2020).

Then, the researchers added the variable of sales promotion because, based on previous research, there is a need to explore the influence of sales promotion on continuance intention (Xavier & Zakkariya, 2021). Sales promotion is a crucial component in marketing and the most effective promotion method to inspire and stimulate faster and more effective responses to the sales of specific products or services. It provides several benefits, including motivating and influencing consumer purchasing decisions, attracting new customers, retaining customers from switching to other competitors, increasing sales volume, and improving profitability (Xavier & Zakkariya, 2021). Several researchers have found that sales promotion significantly influences consumers' continuance intention, this indicates that the better the sales promotion offered, the higher its impact on consumers' continued intention (Fahera, 2020; Lim et al., 2021), however on the other hand there is still research which finds show that sales promotion has no effect on continuance intention (Khare et al., 2020; Ojiaku & Osarenkhoe, 2018).

Another factor that influences continuance intention is hedonic motivation. Online shopping site operators need to pay attention to other factors because consumers not only require ease of use and benefits but also seek an enjoyable experience while shopping online (Prakosa & Sumantika, 2021). Due to the feelings of joy and pleasure when using an online shopping platform, hedonic motivation becomes a strong predictor in the adoption of technology by consumers (Tak & Panwar, 2017). In line with the findings of several researchers, it has been observed that continuance intention is significantly and positively influenced by hedonic motivation (Ashfaq et al., 2019; Chopdar & Sivakumar, 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Xavier & Zakkariya, 2021). However, that study contradicts with research that not find a significant relationship between hedonic motivation and continuance intention (Tam et al., 2020).

The differences in previous research findings that still exist create a research gap. Therefore, to fill this research gap, it is hypothesized that there may be factors that could indirectly influence the results. In this study, the variable of attitude will be added with the aim of addressing the research gap caused by discrepancies in previous research findings. Attitude is included as a mediating variable on the influence of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, sales promotion and hedonic motivation on continuance intention. The factor that also plays a crucial role in the decision for continuous or sustained use of technology is the consumer's attitude towards usage, this is because this factor has a positive influence on the continuity of usage intention by consumers (Rotib et al., 2021). Attitude is also the most significant predictor of continuance intention (Zainal, 2020). Continuance intention will be positively and significantly influenced through attitude by perceived

usefulness (Wang et al., 2020). Variabel attitude is predicted to act as a mediator between perceived ease of use and continuance intention because there is evidence that continuance intention is significantly influenced by attitude. Additionally, perceived ease of use significantly influences attitude and the researchers also explain that consumers who perceive online shopping as something easy will have a more positive attitude and, consequently, a continued intention to shop online (Wu & Song, 2021). The variable attitude is considered a mediating variable between sales promotion and continuance intention, this consideration is based on research that states continuance intention is significantly influenced by attitude, additionally, another researcher found that attitude is positively and significantly influenced by sales promotion (Fam et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Wu & Song, 2021). Furthermore, the attitude variable can be used as a mediator variable between hedonic motivation and continuance intention (Qing & Haiying, 2021).

Referring to studies from several previous studies that there are research gaps, it is necessary to conduct further studies regarding the influence of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, sales promotion, and hedonic motivation on continuance intention through attitude among users of the Shopee marketplace application in East Java, Indonesia.

2. Materials and Methods

This research applies quantitative method, and employs explanatory research. The sampling technique is non- probability sampling with a purposive sampling approach. The respondents in this study are users of the Shopee application on smartphones located in East Java, Indonesia. The selection of respondents in this study was based on the following criteria: (a) Respondents are aged 17 years and above because at that age, an individual is considered an adult and capable of making decisions independently; (b) Respondents currently reside in East Java; (c) Respondents are aware of the Shopee marketplace in Indonesia; (d) Respondents have the Shopee application on their smartphones; and (e) Respondents have used the Shopee marketplace through the smartphone application at least once.

Research respondent number was determined based on the rule of thumb stated by (Hair et al., 2021). Based on the rule of thumb, this research determined the number of samples as equal to the number of research indicator multiplied by 10. The data collection technique in this study was conducted using a questionnaire given indirectly to respondents through Google Forms, while measurement scale was performed using Likert Scale (range from 1 to 5). Questionnaire collected from respondents was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling supported by SmartPLS Applications 3.2.9.

The variables in this study use indicators as measuring tools adopted from several previous studies. The Perceived Usefulness variable in this study was measured using 3 indicators referring to the research of (Tandon et al., 2016). The Perceived Ease of Use variable is measured using 6 indicators which refers to the research of (Iriani & Andjarwati, 2020). The Sales Promotion variable is measured using 3 indicators (Yahya et al., 2019). The Hedonic Motivation variable in this study was measured using 6 indicators referring to the research from (Arnold & Reynolds, 2003; Parker & Wang, 2016). The Attitude variable in this study was measured using 2 indicators referring to the research of (Fong, 2013). Last, the continuance intention variable in this study was measured using 4 indicators referring to the research of (Nugraheni et al., 2020).

This research focuses on analyzing the relationship between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, sales promotion, hedonic motivation, attitude, and continuance intention among users of the Shopee marketplace application in East Java, Indonesia. The variables in this study include independent variables, namely perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, sales promotion, and

hedonic motivation, while the dependent variable is continuance intention. Additionally, the study explores the mediating variable, attitude.

Source: Developed for thesis study, 2023

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

Based on this conceptual framework, the hypotheses in this research are:

- H1: Perceived usefulness influences continuance intention.
- H2: Perceived ease of use influences continuance intention.
- H3: Sales promotion influences continuance intention.
- H4: Hedonic motivation influences continuance intention.
- H5: Attitude influences continuance intention.
- H6: Perceived usefulness influences attitude.
- H7: Perceived ease of use influences attitude.
- H8: Sales promotion influences attitude.
- H9: Hedonic motivation influences attitude.
- H10: Perceived usefulness influences continuance intention through attitude.
- H11: Perceived ease of use influences continuance intention through attitude.
- H12: Sales promotion influences continuance intention through attitude.
- H13: Hedonic motivation influences continuance intention through attitude.

3. Results and Discussions

Based on the results of respondent data processing, it is known that out of 240 respondents, there are 86 male respondents (35.8%) and 154 female respondents (64.2%). This shows that female consumers are more inclined to engage in online shopping activities, especially through the Shopee marketplace application, compared to male consumers. The next category is based on the age of the respondent, there are 48 (20%) respondents with an age range of 17-25 years, 147 respondents (61.3%) with an age range 26-35 years, 34 respondents (14,2%) with an age range of 36 and 45 years, and 11 respondents (4.6%) with an age range of 46 and 55 years. It can be said that the majority of Shopee application users in East Java fall within the age range of 26-35 years. Based on marital status, there are 125 unmarried respondents (52.1%) and 115 married respondents (47.9%). This indicates that unmarried consumers are more interested in engaging in online shopping activities through the Shopee application. Based on education, there are 26 respondents with a high school or equivalent education level (10.8%), 11 respondents (4,6%) with a Diploma (D3) education level, 171

respondents (71,3%) with a Bachelor's degree (S1) education level, and 31 respondents (12,9%) with a Postgraduate (S2/S3) education level. It can be interpreted that the majority of Shopee application users in East Java are bachelor's degree (S1) graduates.

Based on occupation, there are 34 respondents (14,2%) with the occupation of Student/Student, 26 respondents (10,8%) with the occupation of civil servants (PNS), 111 respondents (46,3%) with the occupation of Private Sector/State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) employees, 50 respondents (20,8%) with the occupation of entrepreneurs (20.8%), and 19 respondents (7,9%) unemployed. This explains that the majority of Shopee application users are Private Sector/State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) employees who have income and relatively high purchasing power. In terms of income, respondents with a monthly income of 1 – 3 million are 114 respondents (47.5%), monthly income of >3 – 6 million are 90 respondents (37.5%), monthly income of >6 – 9 million are 19 respondents (7.9%), and monthly income of >9 million are 17 respondents (7.1%). This can be interpreted as the majority of Shopee application users having income in the range of 1 to 3 million per month. Based on the frequency of Shopee application usage, respondents who use the application once are 11 respondents (9.2%), 2 – 5 times are 46 respondents (19.2%), and more than 5 times are 183 respondents (76.3%). These results explain that respondents are users who are already quite familiar with the use of the Shopee application, having used the service more than 5 times.

The next category is based on the domicile, respondents residing in Batu City are 13 respondents (5.4%), Blitar City are 15 respondents (6.3%), Kediri City are 12 respondents (5%), Madiun City are 14 respondents (5.8%), Malang City are 34 respondents (14.2%), Mojokerto City are 8 respondents (3.3%), Pasuruan City are 10 respondents (4.2%), Probolinggo City are 6 respondents (2.5%), Surabaya City are 21 respondents (8.8%), Bangkalan Regency are 3 respondents (1.3%), Banyuwangi Regency are 3 respondents (1.3%), Bojonegoro Regency are 5 respondents (2.1%), Gresik Regency are 5 respondents (2.1%), Jember Regency are 2 respondents (0.8%), Jombang Regency are 7 respondents (2.9%), Lamongan Regency are 2 respondents (0.8%), Lumajang Regency are 3 respondents (1.3%), Magetan Regency are 6 respondents (2.5%), Malang Regency are 11 respondents (4.6%), Ngawi Regency are 7 respondents (2.9%), Pacitan Regency are 6 respondents (2.5%), Pamekasan Regency are 5 respondents (2.1%), Pasuruan Regency are 6 respondents (2.5%), Ponorogo Regency are 5 respondents (2.1%), Sidoarjo Regency are 7 respondents (2.9%), Situbondo Regency are 2 respondents (0.8%), Sumenep Regency are 3 respondents (1.3%), Trenggalek Regency are 8 respondents (3.3%), Tuban Regency are 2 respondents (0.8%), and Tulungagung Regency are 7 respondents (2.9%). This shows that Shopee users are dominated by respondents from Malang City, Surabaya City, Blitar City, and Madiun City. Lastly, based on the category of products purchased, in this category, respondents are allowed to choose more than one category of products they have purchased. Respondents who have purchased fashion products are 140 respondents (29.7%), electronic product purchases are 62 respondents (13.1%), purchases of cosmetics and skincare products are 109 respondents (23.1%), purchases of household items are 81 respondents (17.2%), purchases of books and office supplies are 35 respondents (7.4%), and other products are 45 respondents (9.5%). This indicates that the fashion product category is the most frequently purchased category by respondents on the Shopee application in East Java.

Partial Least Square (PLS) Analysis

The SEM method based on Partial Least Square (PLS) is used as a data processing technique in this research. Researchers used PLS software, namely SmartPLS version 3.2.9, which was developed by the SmartPLS GmbH firm located in Oststeinbek, Germany. PLS is a strong analysis method because it eliminates the assumptions of OLS (Ordinary Least Square) regression, such as data must be normally distributed in a multivariate manner and there is no multicollinearity between independent variables

(Ghozali & Kusumadewi, 2023). The PLS method consists of two basic stages, namely validating the measurement model (outer model) to see how each indicator can present its variables and testing the structural model (inner model) to see the relationship between variables.

Model Evaluation (Outer Model and Inner Model)

Apart from the tests above, researchers also tested the estimation of path coefficients which identify the strength of the relationship between latent variables, both directly and indirectly. This test was carried out using the bootstrapping method using SmartPLS software version 3.2.9.

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Figure 3. Measurement Model (Outer Loading)

Information:

- PU : Perceived Usefulness
- PEOU : Perceived Ease of Use
- SP : Sales Promotion
- HM : Hedonic Motivation
- ATT : Attitude
- CI : Continuance Intention

There are three assessments of the measurement model (outer model) in the data analysis technique with SmartPLS, namely the validity test and the reliability test. The validity test consists of

convergent validity and discriminant validity, while the reliability test consists of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. Convergent validity (validity test) is carried out to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). Based on Figure 3 above, it can be concluded that the items from the indicators for each variable perceived usefulness (X1), perceived ease of use (X2), sales promotion (X3), hedonic motivation (X4), attitude (Z), and continuance intention (Y) have met the requirements for convergent validity, because they have a value loading factor >0.7 .

Table 2
Discriminant Validity Test Results

	PU	PEOU	SP	HM	ATT	CI
PU1	0.784	-0.111	-0.107	0.095	-0.021	-0.065
PU2	0.701	-0.055	-0.097	0.084	0.013	-0.039
PU3	0.763	-0.071	-0.145	0.116	-0.013	-0.048
PU4	0.729	-0.097	-0.105	0.159	-0.004	-0.010
PU5	0.756	-0.045	-0.135	0.205	-0.021	-0.041
PU6	0.775	-0.089	-0.136	0.078	-0.026	-0.044
PU7	0.784	-0.090	0.002	0.115	0.034	-0.023
PU8	0.873	-0.108	-0.052	0.030	0.017	-0.127
PEOU1	-0.108	0.823	0.319	0.331	0.405	0.427
PEOU2	-0.031	0.842	0.305	0.354	0.419	0.396
PEOU3	-0.036	0.785	0.311	0.419	0.393	0.356
PEOU4	-0.203	0.717	0.322	0.209	0.335	0.373
PEOU5	-0.058	0.777	0.326	0.454	0.369	0.428
PEOU6	-0.102	0.817	0.386	0.397	0.440	0.507
SP1	-0.129	0.359	0.896	0.318	0.390	0.491
SP2	-0.122	0.369	0.928	0.303	0.422	0.493
SP3	-0.045	0.360	0.783	0.248	0.382	0.351
HM1	0.161	0.385	0.330	0.810	0.310	0.411
HM2	0.170	0.407	0.332	0.812	0.317	0.459
HM3	0.092	0.386	0.246	0.822	0.313	0.427
HM4	0.116	0.369	0.256	0.835	0.334	0.417
HM5	0.094	0.407	0.286	0.817	0.322	0.399
HM6	-0.002	0.386	0.235	0.788	0.372	0.439
HM7	0.128	0.354	0.237	0.722	0.358	0.398
HM8	0.162	0.329	0.307	0.722	0.293	0.391
HM9	0.155	0.304	0.243	0.731	0.352	0.401
HM10	0.067	0.289	0.234	0.722	0.320	0.360
HM11	0.023	0.341	0.236	0.794	0.315	0.407
HM12	0.015	0.343	0.245	0.791	0.316	0.397
HM13	0.118	0.304	0.168	0.787	0.286	0.341
HM14	0.014	0.366	0.244	0.784	0.252	0.375
HM15	0.125	0.302	0.193	0.796	0.254	0.341
HM16	0.091	0.357	0.298	0.754	0.272	0.371
HM17	0.102	0.320	0.254	0.742	0.315	0.422
HM18	0.117	0.307	0.234	0.755	0.334	0.368
HM19	0.108	0.345	0.272	0.799	0.252	0.382
HM20	0.015	0.448	0.340	0.778	0.499	0.522

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	PU	PEOU	SP	HM	ATT	CI
HM21	0.032	0.372	0.249	0.795	0.339	0.427
HM22	0.035	0.353	0.252	0.803	0.329	0.424
ATT1	-0.029	0.489	0.442	0.428	0.924	0.642
ATT2	0.029	0.407	0.381	0.321	0.889	0.541
CI1	-0.147	0.456	0.435	0.415	0.599	0.890
CI2	-0.041	0.445	0.478	0.488	0.565	0.931
CI3	-0.039	0.508	0.471	0.488	0.658	0.905
CI4	-0.094	0.436	0.431	0.446	0.470	0.784

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Discriminant validity is used to compare loading values to find out whether the construct has adequate discriminant, where the value of the targeted construct must be greater than the value of other constructs. Based on Table 2 above, it can be concluded that the indicators for the variables perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, sales promotion, hedonic motivation, attitude, and continuance intention have met the criteria for discriminant validity.

Table 3

Composite Reliability Results

Variabel	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Perceived Usefulness	0.922	0.910	Reliabel
Perceived Ease of Use	0.911	0.883	Reliabel
Sales Promotion	0.904	0.839	Reliabel
Hedonic Motivation	0.972	0.969	Reliabel
Attitude	0.902	0.785	Reliabel
Continuance Intention	0.931	0.901	Reliabel

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Composite reliability is considered better in estimating the internal consistency of a construct because it is able to measure the true value of the reliability of a construct. Based on the composite reliability results in Table 3 above, the instrument in this study meets the reliability requirements, because it has a composite reliability value of >0.7. So it can be concluded that the construct has good reliability. Structural model testing (inner model) to see the relationship between the significance value of R-square (R²) of the model used. The structural model in PLS is tested by measuring the R² value and path coefficient through comparing the t-statistics with the t-table in the SmartPLS output.

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023
 Figure 4. Structural Model (Inner Model)

Table 4
 R-Square Value

Variabel	R Square
Attitude	0,353
Continuance Intention	0,564

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Table 4 shows the attitude (Z) variable which is influenced by perceived usefulness (X1), perceived ease of use (X2), sales promotion (X3), and hedonic motivation (X4), with an R-square value of 0.353. The R-Square value shows that 35.3% of the attitude can be influenced by perceived usefulness (X1), perceived ease of use (X2), sales promotion (X3), and hedonic motivation (X4), while the remaining 64.7% is influenced by other variables outside the variables studied. Meanwhile, the R-Square value for continuance intention (Y) is 0.564, indicating that 56.4% of the continuance intention variable is influenced by perceived usefulness (X1), perceived ease of use (X2), sales promotion (X3), hedonic motivation (X4), and attitude (Z), while the remaining 43.6% is influenced by other variables outside the variables studied.

Hypothesis Test

Table 5
Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	Original Samples (O)	t-statistic	P value	Description
PU → CI	-0.079	1.272	0.204	Insignificant
PEOU → CI	0.127	2.387	0.017	Significant
SP → CI	0.188	3.272	0.001	Significant
HM → CI	0.241	5.176	0.000	Significant
ATT → CI	0.406	6.476	0.000	Significant
PU → ATT	0.044	0.650	0.516	Insignificant
PEOU → ATT	0.306	3.777	0.000	Significant
SP → ATT	0.274	4.060	0.000	Significant
HM → ATT	0.182	3.148	0.002	Significant
PU → ATT → CI	0.018	0.645	0.519	Insignificant
PEOU → ATT → CI	0.124	3.662	0.000	Significant
SP → ATT → CI	0.111	3.206	0.001	Significant
HM → ATT → CI	0.074	2.778	0.006	Significant

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on the results of the hypothesis test in Table 5 above, it is known that perceived usefulness has a negative and insignificant effect on continuance intention, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (1.272) < t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.204) > 0.05, thus H1 is rejected. Meanwhile, perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on continuance intention, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (2.387) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.017) < 0.05, thus H2 is accepted. Next, sales promotion has a positive and significant effect on continuance intention, the analysis results show the t-statistic value (3.272) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.001) < 0.05, thus H3 is accepted. Meanwhile, hedonic motivation has a positive and significant effect on continuance intention, the analysis results show the t-statistic value (5.176) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.000) < 0.05, thus H4 is accepted. Next, attitude has a positive and significant effect on continuance intention, the analysis results show the t-statistic value (6.476) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.000) < 0.05, thus H5 is accepted.

The next results of the analysis, shows that perceived usefulness has a positive and insignificant effect on continuance intention, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (0.650) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.516) > 0.05, thus H6 is rejected. Meanwhile, perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on attitude, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (3.777) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.000) < 0.05, thus H7 is accepted. Next, sales promotion has a positive and significant effect on attitude, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (4.060) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.000) < 0.05, thus H8 is accepted. Meanwhile, hedonic motivation has a positive and significant effect on attitude, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (3.148) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.002) < 0.05, thus H9 is accepted.

The results of the mediation test on the indirect influence of perceived usefulness on continuance intention through attitude obtained a t-statistic value (0.645) < t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.519) > 0.05, thus H10 is rejected. Next, the indirect influence of perceived ease of use on continuance intention through attitude obtained a t-statistic value (3.662) > t-table value

(1.96) and the p value (0.000) > 0.05, thus H11 is accepted. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of sales promotion on continuance intention through attitude obtained a t-statistic value (3.206) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.001) > 0.05, thus H12 is accepted. Next, the last one the indirect influence of hedonic motivation on continuance intention through attitude obtained a t-statistic value (2.778) > t-table value (1.96) and the p value (0.006) > 0.05, thus H13 is accepted.

Discussion

The Influence of Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention

The results of the analysis show that perceived usefulness have a negative and insignificant effect on continuance intention. This indicates that, the lower the perceived usefulness, the lower the continuance intention of consumers. It can be interpreted that perceived usefulness, in this study, has not emerged as a significant factor influencing continuance intention on the Shopee online shopping application. This lack of influence may be attributed to differences in respondent characteristics and habits in deriving benefits from the Shopee application. Additionally, it is likely that a significant portion of respondents may not heavily rely on perceived benefits when using the Shopee application. This finding contradicts the research by (Wu & Song, 2021), which concludes that consumers who perceive online shopping as beneficial will develop a continuance intention.

The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which shows that perceived usefulness does not significantly influence continuance intention (Ferdianto, 2022; Sarkar & Khare, 2019; Sinaga et al., 2021; Utami et al., 2022). Another previous research explained the concept of perceived usefulness and its relation to technology usage, highlighting that if technology is too difficult to use, there may be a perception that the performance benefits do not justify the effort. The sentence concludes by stating that the study found that perceived usefulness does not significantly influence continuance intention (Munthaha et al., 2023).

The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention

The results of the analysis show that perceived ease of use have a positive and significant effect on continuance intention. This indicates that when consumers perceive that the Shopee application provides utility, they intend to reuse the service. Additionally, the easier the Shopee application is for consumers to use, the more it enhances their continuance intention toward the application. The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which shows that perceived ease of use significantly and positively influences consumers' continuance intention in online and mobile application purchases (Nugraheni et al., 2020; Omotayo & Omotope, 2018). Additionally, consistent with the research by (Nabila et al., 2023) it is revealed that perceived ease of use has a positive influence on continuance intention in the Shopee marketplace. The study suggests that the convenience of using the Shopee platform can contribute to consumer satisfaction, as it is easily comprehensible. Consequently, the positive establishment of perceived ease of use among consumers will stimulate positive consumer behavioral intentions.

The Influence of Sales Promotion on Continuance Intention

The results of the analysis show that sales promotion have a positive and significant effect on continuance intention. This indicates that sales promotion has an impact on increasing continuance intention among consumers. The better the sales promotion offered by Shopee to consumers, the more interested consumers will become, thereby enhancing continuance intention towards the Shopee application. Sales promotion is a more effective promotion method than others, capable of

driving and influencing the feelings, perceptions, and purchasing decisions of consumer (Chakraborty et al., 2013).

The findings of this study support the results of research conducted by (Fahera, 2020) which suggests the need to include a promotion variable that can influence consumers' continuance intention to shop online. The results indicate that sales promotion significantly influences consumers' continuance intention on the Shopee marketplace. This implies that the better the sales promotion offered, the higher its impact on consumers' sustained intention. These findings align with the research by (Lim et al., 2021; Prakosa & Sumantika, 2021) highlighting that sales promotion, as part of the marketing mix, has a positive impact on continuance intention in retail application.

The Influence of Hedonic Motivation on Continuance Intention

The results of the analysis show that hedonic motivation have a positive and significant effect on continuance intention. This means that the more consumers feel joy and comfort when using the Shopee application, the higher the frequency of consumers using the Shopee application. Consistent with researchers (Tak & Panwar, 2017) who state that the feeling of joy and pleasure when using e-commerce during online shopping makes hedonic motivation a strong predictor in consumer technology adoption. Consumers desire a pleasant experience when shopping online (Prakosa & Sumantika, 2021).

The findings of this research are also in line with the results of previous research conducted by (Ashfaq et al., 2019; Chopdar & Sivakumar, 2019) where it was found that continuance intention is significantly influenced by hedonic motivation in mobile shopping applications in India. Furthermore, a researcher who studied consumer sustained intention in e-commerce in China proved that hedonic motivation, also referred to as perceived enjoyment, is the strongest predictor positively and significantly influencing continuance intention (Ashfaq et al., 2019). Another researcher also argue that hedonic motivation is the strongest factor influencing continuance intention (Wang et al., 2020). Hedonic motivation also found positively and significantly influences continuance intention in the use of mobile applications (Xavier & Zakkariya, 2021).

The Influence of Attitude on Continuance Intention

The results of the analysis show that attitude have a positive and significant effect on continuance intention. This indicates that the more positive the consumer's attitude toward using the Shopee application, the higher the frequency and continuance intention of the consumer using the Shopee application. The results of this study support the findings of research conducted by (Vanduhe et al., 2020), which states that the attitude variable is an important factor that can influence continuance intention in the use of technology. The research results indicate that attitude has a positive and significant impact on continuance intention. According to (Wu & Song, 2021), attitude is a key determinant of whether a consumer will adopt or reject a technology. In their study, it was found that attitude significantly influences consumers' continuance intention for online shopping. This is consistent with the research of (Qing & Haiying, 2021), who investigated the online shopping behavior of Chinese consumers through smartphone apps and found that continuance intention is positively and significantly influenced by attitude.

The Influence of Perceived Usefulness on Attitude

The results of the analysis indicate that no significant relationship was found between perceived usefulness and attitude. This shows that the utility offered by the Shopee application does not quickly and easily change consumers' positive attitudes toward Shopee. The findings of this study align with the research where it was found that perceived usefulness has no significant influence on attitude (Rahmiati & Yuannita, 2019).

The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use on Attitude

The results of the analysis show that perceived ease of use have a positive and significant effect on attitude. This indicates that the easier consumers perceive the Shopee application to be, the more it enhances their positive attitude towards adopting or using the Shopee application. The results of this study are consistent with research that investigated consumer technology acceptance in online shopping, revealing that attitude is significantly influenced by perceived ease of use (Kasilingam, 2020; Zuniarti et al., 2021). Thus, this study aligns with the findings of previous research.

The Influence of Sales Promotion on Attitude

The results of the analysis show that sales promotion have a positive and significant effect on attitude. This shows that the better the sales promotion conducted by Shopee, the more it enhances a positive attitude among consumers toward the Shopee application. This finding aligns with the research conducted by (Aykaç & Yilmaz, 2020), which emphasizes that one of the ways companies can develop and improve positive consumer attitudes is through effective sales promotion. Their study found a significant influence of sales promotion on attitude. Another relevant study indicates that consumers in Indonesia and Malaysia exhibit the highest interest in sales promotions, resulting in the strongest positive attitude and the results of their research also found that attitude is significantly influenced by sales promotion (Fam et al., 2019).

The Influence of Hedonic Motivation on Attitude

The results of the analysis show that hedonic motivation have a positive and significant effect on attitude. This indicates that the more consumers feel pleasure and comfort when using the Shopee application, the more it enhances a positive attitude among consumers toward the Shopee application. The findings of this research are also consistent with the results of previous research that investigated Lazada and Shopee applications, revealing that hedonic motivation significantly influences consumer attitudes in online shopping (Tunsakul, 2020). Another previous study also found that hedonic motivation is the strongest predictor significantly influencing consumer attitudes in conducting online shopping transactions through applications (Pop et al., 2023).

The Influence of Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention Through Attitude

The results of the analysis show that attitude does not act as a mediator in the relationship between perceived usefulness and continuance intention. This means that if consumers perceive the Shopee application as less useful, a positive attitude is not formed by consumers.

The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention Through Attitude

The results of the analysis show that perceived ease of use have a positive and significant effect on continuance intention through attitude. This indicates that the easier consumers feel when using the Shopee application, the more it will enhance a positive attitude among consumers, ultimately resulting in an increase in consumers' continuance intention towards the Shopee application.

The findings of this research align with the research conducted by (Wang et al., 2020), indicating that perceived ease of use can influence continuance intention through attitude. Furthermore, consumers who perceive online shopping as easy tend to have a more positive attitude and develop a continuance intention to shop online (Wu & Song, 2021). The results of this study are also consistent with research that found a significant relationship between perceived ease of use and continuance intention through attitude, this means that the higher the perceived ease of use, the more positive the

consumer's attitude, indirectly leading to an increased intention to continue using the online application (Ali, 2017).

The Influence of Sales Promotion on Continuance Intention Through Attitude

The results of the analysis show that sales promotion have a positive and significant effect on continuance intention through attitude. That can be interpreted as the better the sales promotions offered by Shopee perceived by consumers, the emergence of a positive attitude perceived from consumers' evaluations after using the Shopee application, thus capable of increasing continuance intention towards the Shopee application. This result supports the findings of research conducted by (Fam et al., 2019), stating that sales promotion significantly influences attitude, as well as research stating that attitude significantly influences continuance intention (Wang et al., 2020; Wu & Song, 2021).

The Influence of Hedonic Motivation on Continuance Intention Through Attitude

The results of the analysis show that hedonic motivation have a positive and significant effect on continuance intention through attitude. This means that the more consumers feel pleasure and comfort when using the Shopee application, it leads to the emergence of a positive attitude perceived by consumers in their evaluation after using the Shopee application, thereby enhancing continuance intention toward the Shopee application. This result supports the findings of the research conducted by (Wang et al., 2020) indicating that hedonic motivation can influence continuance intention through attitude. Furthermore, consistent with the study by (Qing & Haiying, 2021) it was found that attitude can mediate the relationship between hedonic motivation and continuance intention.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis and discussions, it can be concluded that perceived ease of use, sales promotion, and hedonic motivation have a positive and significant influence on attitude. Furthermore, they also have a positive and significant impact on continuance intention, both directly and indirectly through attitude. Consumers will consider the aspects of the ease of service in the Shopee application and, subsequently, how the sales promotions offered by Shopee can influence them. Then, consumers experience pleasure and comfort when using the Shopee application. If these aspects are fulfilled, a positive attitude will emerge among consumers, ultimately enhancing their intention to continue using the Shopee application.

Meanwhile, for perceived usefulness, no significant results were found regarding attitude, and no significant results were found either for continuance intention, both directly and indirectly through attitude. Therefore, Shopee's management is expected to pay attention to and enhance services as well as supporting features in the application to increase the perceived usefulness for consumers. This, in turn, may shape a positive attitude among consumers and further encourage them to continue using the Shopee application.

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